

Spectrophotometric Determination of Copper with Chromotropic Acid Azo Dyes of the Pyridine Series

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Copper forms coloured complexes with the azo dyes of the pyridine series, e.g., 2-(pyridyl-2-azo)chromotropic acid (A) and 2-(pyridyl-3-azo)chromotropic acid (B). Both the reagents combine with copper in a metal to reagent ratio of 1:3 with instability constants in the order of 10^{-13} and 10^{-15} . The systems obey Beer's law a 580 m μ with the optimum range from 0.5 to 2.0 p.p.m. with Reagent A and at 570 m μ with the optimum range from 1.0 to 4.0 p.p.m. with Reagent B. The reagents are extremely sensitive towards copper and the sensitivities, calculated according to Sandell, are 0.00283 γ/cm^2 and 0.00930 γ/cm^2 , respectively.

Of the derivatives of chromotropic acid, 2,7-dinitroso-¹ and 7-nitroso-chromotropic² acids were observed to exhibit colour reactions with copper. The former reagent was not, however, thoroughly investigated for its use as a spectrophotometric reagent and the latter was claimed to be more effective though it lacked in specificity and selectivity. Arsenazo I³ and II⁴ also suffer from the same defects. During a study of the reactive groupings of the azo dyes, Alexander⁵ found -OH, *ortho* to azo, to be the most effective colour-forming group for copper.

The present communication describes the reaction of trace quantities of copper with two sensitive chromotropic acid azo dyes, e.g., 2-(pyridyl-2-azo)chromotropic acid (Na-salt) (Reagent A) and 2-(pyridyl-3-azo)chromotropic acid (Na-salt) (Reagent B).

The coloured systems formed by Reagents A and B at a respective pH 2.8-3.5 and 7.0-8.0 show absorption maxima at 580 and 570 m μ , respectively. These systems obey Beer's law with optimum ranges⁶ from 0.5 to 2.0 p.p.m. of copper with Reagent A and from 1.0 to 4.0 p.p.m. of copper with Reagent B, where the % relative errors⁷ are only 2.85 and 2.80, respectively.

7. Ayres, *Anal. Chem.*, 1949, **21**, 652.

1. Steigman, *J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1943, **62**, 42; *Chem. Abs.*, 1943, **37**, 3689.

2. Datta and Saha, *Microchim. Acta*, 1961, **3**, 361.

3. Zaikovskii and Gerkhardt, *Zhur. Anal. Khim.*, 1953, **13**, 274; *Anal. Abs.*, 1959, **6**, 1255.

4. Kuznetsov *et al.*, *Radiokhim.*, 1959, **1**, 589; *Anal. Abs.*, 1961, **8**, 2395.

5. *Analyst*, 1947, **72**, 56.

6. Ringbom, *Z. anal. Chem.*, 1938/39, **115**, 332.

Both the reagents combine with copper in a metal to reagent ratio of 1:3 with instability constants in the order of 10^{-13} (Reagent A) and 10^{-15} (Reagent B). The composition suggests that one of the reagent molecules is acting purely as electron donors and the other two are utilised to satisfy the primary and secondary valencies of copper.⁸

Possibly the steric effect offered by the bulky carboxy group, *ortho* to pyridine nitrogen, prevents 2-(2-carboxypyridyl-3-azo)chromotropic acid (Na-salt):

from forming any coloured complex with copper.

Reagent A is more sensitive and effective as a reagent than Reagent B. Its molar extinction coefficient for copper is 22440 as compared to the latter's value of 6831, whereas the sensitivities are $0.00283 \text{ } \gamma/\text{cm}^2$ and $0.00930 \text{ } \gamma/\text{cm}^2$, respectively.

EXPERIMENTAL

A Uvispek spectrophotometer and a Cambridge pH indicator were used for the absorbance and the pH measurements, respectively.

Chemicals used were all of reagent quality and their solutions were prepared always in double distilled water.

A standard copper salt solution was prepared from copper sulphate of E. Merck. An aliquot portion of the solution on analysis by the usual iodometric method provided 1.083 mg. of copper per ml. Weaker solutions were prepared, as needed, by proper dilutions.

Reagents A and B were prepared by following the methods described earlier⁹. Reagent solutions of 0.05% w/v were prepared and used.

Buffer A of pH 2.8 was prepared by mixing 1.0N solution of sodium acetate with the required amount of 1.0N-HCl. Buffer B of pH 8.0 was prepared by adjusting the pH of a 5% (w/v) ammonium chloride solution with 1:2 ammonia. The pHs of the buffers were checked everyday before use.

A standard solution of sodium perchlorate of ionic strength 1.25μ was prepared and 0.5 ml of this solution was used every time to maintain the ionic strength to 0.025μ in a total volume of 25 ml.

Spectral Transmittancy Curve.—Aliquot portions of the standard copper sulphate solution were taken in 25-ml flasks and to the one containing 25 μg . of copper were added 2.5 ml of Reagent A and 1 ml of buffer A; to the other with 50 μg . of copper were added 2.5 ml of Reagent B, 4 ml of ethanol, and 1 ml of buffer B. The pHs of the mixtures were thus

adjusted to 2.8 and 8.0, respectively, and then the mixtures were made to volume with

FIG. 1
Curve 1. Cu^{2+} —Reagent A.
2. Cu^{2+} —Reagent B.

The copper-Reagent A system at pH 2.8 was stable for 60 min., whereas the copper-Reagent B system was stable for 80 min. at pH 8.0.

Beer's Law Curve, Optimum Range, and Photometric Error.—The colour systems obeyed Beer's law from 0.5 to 2.5 p.p.m. with Reagent A and 0.4 to 3.4 p.p.m. with Reagent B.

To evaluate optimum ranges and analytical accuracy, Ringbom's curves⁶ were drawn by plotting % absorbance as ordinate against log concentration as abscissa. Thus the optimum concentration with the highest accuracy ranges from 0.5 to 2.0 p.p.m. with Reagent A and from 1.0 to 4.0 p.p.m. with Reagent B (Fig. 2), where the curves have the steepest slopes and the percentage relative errors per 1% absolute photometric error⁷ for the said ranges are, respectively, 2.85 and 2.80.

Effect of Diverse Ions.—The effect of diverse ions was studied by following the procedure, described above, with varying concentrations of each of the ionic species to be

distilled water. These procedures were repeated in all the experiments described hereafter. Reagent blanks were also prepared in a similar way. Optical densities of the test and reagent solutions against water blank and of the test solutions against reagent blanks were measured and plotted in Fig. 1. The curves show the complexes to have maximum absorption at 580 mμ with Reagent A and at 570 mμ with Reagent B.

Effect of pH, Reagent, and Time.—The intensity of colour of the system with Reagent A was found to increase with the pH up to 2.8; from 2.8 to 3.5, it remained constant and again over pH 4.5, it showed the same tendency to increase. All subsequent measurements were therefore made between the pH 2.8 and 3.5.

The absorbance of the system with Reagent B also increased with the pH up to 7.0; it maintained constant absorbance over the pH 7.0 to 8.0, then decreased on further increase of pH. Measurements of absorbances for the copper-Reagent B system were therefore made at a pH between 7.0 and 8.0.

Reagent solutions (2.5 ml), A and B respectively, were required for the maximum colour development with 25 μg. and 50 μg. of copper in a total volume of 25 ml. Addition of more reagent had no adverse effect on the optical density as long as measurements were made against a reagent blank.

FIG. 2
Standard curves: 1. Cu^{2+} —Reagent A.
2. Cu^{2+} —Reagent B.

examined. A difference of more than 0.005 in absorbance unit was arbitrarily taken as an interference. The ions, which have been found to interfere in the determination of copper with both the reagents, are cerous, ceric, stannous, stannic, oxalate, phosphate, and fluoride. Tolerance limits of other ions are as shown in Table I.

TABLE I

Ions.	Added as.	Max. tolerance limit (p.p.m.).		Ions.	Added as.	Max. tolerance limit (p.p.m.).	
		Reagent A.	Reagent B			Reagent A.	Reagent B.
Li ⁺	LiCl	200	200	Cr ³⁺	Cr ₂ (SO ₄) ₃	200	20
Ba ²⁺	BaCl ₂	200	200	W ⁶⁺	(NH ₄) ₂ WO ₄	50	200
Zn ²⁺	ZnSO ₄	200	50	Mo ⁶⁺	(NH ₄) ₂ MoO ₄	50	200
Sr ²⁺	Sr(NO ₃) ₂	200	200	Fe ³⁺	FeCl ₃	50	200
Pb ²⁺	Pb(NO ₃) ₂	Ppt.	Ppt.	Th ⁴⁺	Th(NO ₃) ₄	Interferes	50
Cd ²⁺	Cd(NO ₃) ₂	200	200	UO ₂ ²⁺	UO ₂ (NO ₃) ₂	200	200
Be ²⁺	Be(NO ₃) ₂	200	Interferes	As ⁵⁺	Na ₃ AsO ₄	20	20
Hg ²⁺	HgCl ₂	200	200	V ⁵⁺	NH ₄ VO ₃	200	200
Ni ²⁺	NiSO ₄	50	Interferes	Tartrate	NH ₄ -tartrate	100	Interferes
Mg ²⁺	MgSO ₄	200	200	Citrate	NH ₄ -citrate	20	..
Co ²⁺	Co(NO ₃) ₂	50	Interferes	EDTA	Di-Na-salt	Interferes	..
Mn ²⁺	MnSO ₄	200	200				

Composition of the Complexes.—The composition of the complexes of copper with the

$$[\text{Cu}]/([\text{Cu}]+[\text{R}]) \rightarrow$$

FIG. 3. Job's method (equimol.).

- 1—Cu²⁺=Reagent A $\times 1.7905 \times 10^{-4}M$.
- 2— .. = A $\times 2.0 \times 10^{-4}M$.
- 3— .. = B $\times 3.0 \times 10^{-4}M$.
- 4— .. = B $\times 4.0 \times 10^{-4}M$.

reagents was studied by Job's method⁹ of continued variation, as modified by Vosburgh and Cooper¹⁰, as well as by molar and slope-ratio methods. For Job's method, equimolar solutions of copper and the reagents were mixed in different metal to reagent ratio and their absorbances were measured against water as blank. In both the systems, copper reacts in a ratio of 1:3 with the reagents (Fig. 3).

For the molar ratio method¹¹, solutions were prepared with a constant concentration of copper but with the varying ratio of the moles of the reagent to the moles of copper. The absorbances of these solutions were measured against reagent blanks. The curves in Fig. 4 show sharp breaks at the molar ratio of 1:3 with both the reagents.

In order to apply the slope-ratio method¹², two series of solutions were prepared for each colour system. One series contained constant excess of copper with varying amounts of the reagent and in the other series, the quantities of the reagent and copper were

9. *Compt. rend.*, 1925, **180**, 928; *Ann. chim.*, 1928, **x**, 9, 113.

10. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, **63**, 437.

11. Yoe and Jones, *Ind. Eng. Chem., Anal. Ed.*, 1944, **16**, 111.

12. Harvey and Manning, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, **72**, 4488; 1952, **74**, 4744.

13. Sandell, "Colorimetric Determination of Traces of Metals", Interscience Publishers Inc., New York 1956, p. 84.

reversed. The absorbances of the solutions, diluted to 25 ml, were measured against water as blank for the first series and the reagent as blank for the second. From Fig. 5, the ratios of the slopes of the curves 1 (Reagent A in excess) and 2 (copper in excess) and those of the curves 3 (Reagent B in excess) and 4 (copper in excess) were calculated as $0.767/0.255$ and $0.527/0.176$, respectively, indicating a ratio of 1:3 (metal: reagent) in both the cases.

Reagent (ml).

FIG. 4. Molar ratio method.

- 1— Cu^{2+} = Reagent A = $2 \times 10^{-4} M$.
 2— Cu^{2+} = Reagent B = $4 \times 10^{-4} M$.
 (2 ml of Cu^{2+} used).

Variants (ml).

FIG. 5. Slope-ratio method.

- 1— $\text{Cu}^{2+} = 1.7905 \times 10^{-4} M$, A = $1.7905 \times 10^{-3} M$.
 2— $\text{Cu}^{2+} = 1.7905 \times 10^{-3} M$, A = $1.7905 \times 10^{-4} M$.
 3— $\text{Cu}^{2+} = 0.5 \times 10^{-4} M$, B = $5 \times 10^{-4} M$.
 4— $\text{Cu}^{2+} = 5 \times 10^{-4} M$, B = $0.5 \times 10^{-4} M$.

Molar Extinction Coefficient, Sensitivity, Degree of Dissociation, and Instability Constant.

—The molar extinction coefficients for copper, as calculated from Beer's law, are 22440 and 6831 with Reagents A and B, respectively, whereas the sensitivities, as calculated according to Sandell¹³, are $0.00283 \gamma/\text{cm}^2$ and $0.00930 \gamma/\text{cm}^2$.

The dissociation constants, K 's, were calculated¹² from the equation:

$$K = \frac{(m \alpha c)^m (n \alpha c)^n}{c(1 - \alpha)}$$

where

$$\alpha = \frac{E_m - E_s}{E_m}$$

TABLE II

Fig. 6.	Cu concn.	Reagent concn.	m.	n.	p.	z.	$K(\text{at } 22^\circ)$.	$K(\text{av.})$.
Curve 1	$2 \times 10^{-4} M$	A — $5 \times 10^{-4} M$	1	3	2.50	0.60	2.0×10^{-13}	2.5×10^{-13}
2	$2 \times 10^{-4} M$	A — $4 \times 10^{-4} M$	1	3	2.00	0.65	3.1×10^{-13}	
3	$3 \times 10^{-4} M$	B — $5 \times 10^{-4} M$	1	3	1.67	0.65	1.05×10^{-13}	3.5×10^{-13}
4	$3 \times 10^{-4} M$	B — $4 \times 10^{-4} M$	1	3	1.33	0.70	6.10×10^{-13}	

and found to be 5.9×10^{-13} and 3.7×10^{-13} (at 22°) with the α values of 0.215 and 0.038, respectively, for Reagents A and B.

With the non-equimolar solutions of copper and the reagents, the dissociation constants, K 's, as calculated according to Job's equation⁹, are recorded in Table II and in Fig 6

FIG. 6. Job's method (non-equimol).